

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF THE CONSUMER MARKET IN ENSURING FOOD SAFETY OF THE REPUBLIC OF AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

The article examines the role of the consumer market in ensuring food security in the Republic of Azerbaijan. The article notes that the creation of a reliable system of providing the country's population with consumer products in the conditions of market relations necessitates the creation of a highly secured consumer market and the importance of regulating this market. It is determined that the first priority of the regulatory impact on the consumer market is to ensure sustainable growth of the market in terms of both consumption and production, which will solve the problem of improving the quality of life of the population and creating multiplier effects, which are interconnected at the macro and regional levels.

Keywords: consumer market, food security, market relations, macroeconomic regulation, level of self-sufficiency, agri-food market, Commodity markets, agro-industrial complexes.

Food, raw materials and agricultural product markets and ensuring their sustainable functioning are one of the priority directions of the agro-industrial and socio-economic policy of our country. In this regard, the level of development of industrial sectors, food sub-complexes (production of means of production, material resources, supply, personnel training, production of agricultural products, storage, processing, wholesale and retail trade and consumption) and the competitiveness of food markets (infrastructure, market conditions, institutions and regulators) determine the state of food and economic security of the state as a whole. Food security, as a general rule, is the main factor of political and economic independence of each state, and it determines the country's food independence. Ensuring food independence of the state directly depends on the regulation of the agricultural sector as a whole, including the consumer market. Each country has a specific set of individual measures to ensure food security and applies them. Almost all of these measures pursue the same goal: to maintain a stable economic situation and a certain level of profitability in agricultural production, to protect the domestic market, etc.

In the conditions of market relations, the creation of a reliable system of providing the country's population with consumer products necessitates the creation of a highly secured consumer market and the importance of regulating this market. It is impossible to talk about providing the population with consumer products without providing the consumer market with sufficient consumer products. Regulation of the consumer market by state and public organizations is a complex and complex process. The first priority of the regulatory impact on the consumer market should be to ensure sustainable growth of the market in terms of both consumption and production. In this case, the consumer market will solve the problem of improving the quality of life of the population and creating multiplier

effects, which are interconnected at the macro and regional levels. In this regard, the experience of countries with a socially oriented market shows that the consumer market, which provides reliable consumer security for the population, is regulated by the state. The direct influence of the state on economic relations in the consumer market and the methods it uses depend on the scale of economic development of each country, its natural characteristics, trends formed in the agricultural sector, and other various factors. In principle, the experience of our country and foreign countries shows that all models and concepts for regulating consumer markets are in one way or another related to achieving a compromise between competition and administrative instruments. Given the comprehensive nature of the consumer market, its highly developed institutional and subjective environment, inconsistency in the manifestation of the forms and methods of influence that seem universal is inevitable.

Studies show that the main criterion for the effectiveness of macroeconomic regulation carried out by the state in the field of food security is the development of productive forces, and this regulation should, first of all, serve to improve the material well-being of the country's population. In the process of forming a consumer market that can ensure food security in our country, along with the full and effective use of the existing potential of the agricultural sector, the processing industry of agricultural products should also develop.

The main directions of the country's agri-food policy are ensuring high quality of agricultural and food products, supporting the competitive advantages of these products both in the domestic market and in foreign trade activities with agricultural and food products.

The conducted studies allow us to say that one of the main tasks in ensuring the country's food security

and regulating the agri-food market is to protect the interests of consumers and agricultural producers, who are participants in the food market. In the mechanism of operation of the agri-food market, which plays a key role in ensuring food security in market relations, the interests of agricultural producers are protected when their activities do not conflict with the interests of producers. Thus, summarizing the above, we can conclude that the main goals in ensuring the food security of the Republic and regulating the agri-food market are the following:

- Increasing the level of food self-sufficiency;
- Increasing the level of food security;
- Achieving price stabilization work during sharp fluctuations in product prices in the agri-food market;
- Formation of coordinated relations of the agricultural sector with other sectors of the national economy;
- Workers operating in the agricultural sector Elimination of inequality between the incomes of farmers and the incomes of workers working in other sectors of the national economy;
- Implementation of measures to protect local food producers from an unfavorable competitive environment in the agri-food market;

An important component of the mechanism for ensuring food security is the regulation of agriculture and the formation of a state support system.

In recent years, an appropriate support system for agricultural producers has been formed by the state, and consistent measures have been taken to improve and increase the transparency of this system. These support measures have been important in terms of strengthening the provision of agricultural producers with appropriate means of production and improving their income-generating opportunities.

The state's agrarian policy has a special role in regulating the agri-food market. In our country, fundamental reforms in agriculture have led to the development of the agrarian sector in order to provide the population

with basic types of food products. The technical and financial assistance provided by the government to agricultural producers and enterprises processing agricultural products is of exceptional importance in the development of agriculture.

The development of competition in the sectors of the national economy and commodity markets and the activation of market incentives for business are essential conditions for increasing the production and export potential of our country's agro-industrial complex and entering the highly competitive markets of third countries.

The existence of systematic and even short-term problems limiting competition in food markets directly leads to a decrease in trade turnover and entrepreneurial activity, a decrease in the quality of manufactured products, work performed, and services provided, and ultimately - a deterioration in the satisfaction of consumers of these products.

The solution to the tasks set involves the implementation of systematic work by relevant state bodies at the national and international levels, ensuring:

- Creation of equal and favorable conditions and incentives for the implementation of activities by business entities aimed at the formation of sustainable and efficient value chains at the international level;
- Reduction of the level of monopolization, optimal concentration of resources of commodity markets, agro-industrial complexes and mixed sectors;
- Stimulation of the entry of new enterprises into commodity markets and cooperation between subjects of the regional agri-food market;
- Improvement of antitrust regulation mechanisms in accordance with international standards of competition law;
- Strengthening the competitiveness of goods, services and business entities produced in our country on the basis of creating a favorable business environment for innovative development, technological and economic progress and increasing production efficiency.

Table 1

Annual per capita consumption rate for staple food products, kg

Products	Scientifically based consumption rate
1.All types of meat and meat products	31,5
2.Milk and dairy products	232,3
3.Eggs (units)	153
4.Sugar and sugar products	17,4
5.Vegetable oils	9,8
6.Fish and fish products	7,7
7.Butter	6,7
8.Bread and bakery products	126,1
9.Potatoes	50,6
10.All types of vegetables	96,9
11.Fruits and berries	46,0

Source: Statistical indicators of the Republic of Azerbaijan

Table 2.

Per capita production of main food products in 2015-2022, kg

№	Ad	2013	2015	2017	2019	2020	2021	2022
1.	All types of meat and meat products	31.0	31.0	33.0	34.0	35.0	35.7	36.8
2.	Milk and dairy products	197.0	202.0	208.0	217.0	220.0	222.0	226.0
3.	Eggs (units)	166.0	163.0	176.0	18.4	191	184	201
4.	Sugar and sugar products	24,5	34.6	24.3	27.1	25.7	33.9	38.3
5.	Vegetable oils	11.2	11.1	8.2	7.5	7.4	7.2	6.7
6.	Fish and fish products	5.3	5.4	6.6	6.4	6.1	5.9	5.9
7.	Butter	2.5	2.5		2.4	2.4	2.6	2.5
8.	Bread and bakery products	125,6	124.8	124,3	125.9	128.6	127.8	124.5
9.	Potatoes	87.0	88.0	94.0	101.0	104.0	106.1	107.4
10.	All types of vegetables	126.0	134.0	144.0	173.0	174.0	181.0	182.0
11.	Fruits and berries	90.0	93.0	98.0	111.0	114.0	120.0	125.3

Source: Statistical indicators of the Republic of Azerbaijan

Within the framework of the research work conducted, the identification, assessment and prediction of factors that negatively affect the competitive environment of food markets and agro-industrial complexes in the market space of our Republic have been identified as an extremely urgent problem. The solution of these identified problems requires the development of effective, coordinated approaches that ensure the creation of

favorable conditions for the formation of sustainable and efficient value chains fully integrated into the global trade system. When examining the problem of the level of food security in the country, it is appropriate to consider the volume, structure and consumption of domestic production of basic food products by comparing the level of demand for basic food products by the population.

Table 3

Per capita consumption of main food products in 2015-2022, kg

№	Ad	2013	2015	2017	2019	2020	2021	2022
1.	All types of meat and meat products	33.4	33.5	37.4	40.8	40.8	41.2	42.1
2.	Milk and dairy products	246.5	246.2	237.1	246.3	257.6	253.3	259.3
3.	Eggs (units)	153	154	158	165	175	170	179
4.	Sugar and sugar products	25.6	21.7	26.3	26.3	26.9	27.3	27.3
5.	Vegetable oils	10.8	12.6	16.0	16.1	15.3	9.4	8.4
6.	Fish and fish products	7.2	7.0	7.9	7.6	7.3	7.4	7.6
7.	Butter	4.7	4.4	3.4	3.3	3.6	3.8	4.0
8.	Bread and bakery products	124.6	124.2	124.3	125.5	128.4	126.2	122.5
9.	Potatoes	72.5	71.6	75.2	82.2	83.3	84.2	91.3
10.	All types of vegetables	108.0	110.4	104.1	127.7	134.1	138.2	139.4
11.	Fruits and berries	66.9	72.7	71.2	80.4	87.4	83.7	79.9

Source: Statistical indicators of the Republic of Azerbaijan 2015-2023

Table 4.

Consumption sufficiency ratio for main food products in 2015-2022

№	Ad	2013	2015	2017	2019	2020	2021	2022
1.	All types of meat and meat products	106,0	106,3	118,7	129,5	129,5	130.8	133.6
2.	Milk and dairy products	106,1	105,9	102,4	106,0	110,9	109.0	111.6
3.	Eggs (units)	100,0	100,6	103,3	107,8	114,4	111.1	117.0
4.	Sugar and sugar products	149,7	124,7	151,1	151,1	154,6	156.9	156.9
5.	Vegetable oils	110,2	128,6	163,3	164,3	156,1	95.9	85.7
6.	Fish and fish products	93,5	90,9	102,6	98,7	94,8	96.1	98.7
7.	Butter	70,1	65,7	50,7	49,2	46,7	56.7	41.2
8.	Bread and bakery products	98,8	98,5	98,6	99,6	101,8	100.0	97.1
9.	Potatoes	143,3	141,5	148,6	162,4	164,6	166.4	180.4
10.	All types of vegetables	111,3	113,8	107,3	131,6	138,4	142.6	143.8
11.	Fruits and berries	145,4	158,0	154,8	174,8	190,4	181.9	173.7

Source: Statistical indicators of the Republic of Azerbaijan 2015-2023

Statistical and calculated data show that in recent years, the consumption sufficiency ratio for basic food products has increased for all other products, except for butter, fish and fish products, compared to the 2013

level, and the food supply process has been in line with medical standards, with the exception of the annual per capita consumption of butter. Table 5

Dynamics of the volume and structure of household per capita income and consumption expenditure by component elements (man)

Composition of income and consumption expenditure	2013		2015		2017		2018		2019		2020	
	man	%										
Income-total	214,7	100,0	240,4	100,0	268,4	100,0	276,0	100,0	292,6	100,0	291,4	100,0
Income from employment	70,7	32,9	78,2	32,5	89,5	33,3	92,4	33,5	99,3	33,9	104,1	35,7
Income from self-employment	55,2	25,7	63,9	26,6	68,6	25,6	70,2	25,4	70,7	24,2	63,4	21,8
Income from agriculture	29,8	13,9	32,1	13,4	35,9	13,4	36,0	13,0	36,4	12,4	34,6	11,9
Income from rental	1,6	0,7	1,7	0,7	1,8	0,7	1,9	0,7	1,9	0,6	1,2	0,4
Income from property	0,5	0,2	0,5	0,2	0,5	0,2	0,6	0,2	0,6	0,2	0,5	0,2
Current transfers received	34,6	16,2	38,0	15,8	41,8	15,6	44,3	16,1	49,3	16,9	57,8	19,8
Other income	22,3	10,4	26,0	10,8	30,3	11,3	30,6	11,1	34,4	11,8	29,8	10,2
Consumption expenditure-total	221,4	100,0	245,6	100,0	278,2	100,0	286,0	100,0	298,4	100,0	297,8	100,0
On food products	91,8	41,5	99,4	40,5	117,4	42,4	119,7	41,8	123,8	41,5	129,2	43,4
On clothing and footwear	15,9	7,2	16,9	6,9	18,0	6,5	18,2	6,4	18,4	6,2	19,0	6,4
On water, electricity, gas, and other types of fuel	17,0	7,7	18,2	7,4	20,5	7,4	21,7	7,6	22,6	7,6	23,5	7,9
On household goods, household appliances	19,8	8,9	23,2	9,4	24,4	8,8	25,2	8,8	25,6	8,6	24,9	8,4
On health services	11,5	4,6	12,0	4,9	13,1	4,7	13,8	4,8	14,4	4,8	14,8	5,0
Transportation expenses	14,2	6,4	15,3	6,2	16,9	6,1	17,7	6,2	19,0	6,4	19,6	6,6
On communication expenses	6,8	3,1	8,2	3,3	9,0	3,2	9,2	3,2	9,7	3,2	9,9	3,3
On other goods and services	45,6	20,6	52,4	21,4	58,9	21,2	60,5	21,2	64,9	21,7	56,9	19,0

The data in Table 5 show that during the years 2013-2022, the consumption expenditures of the population exceeded their incomes. Thus, while in 2013, consumption expenditures exceeded incomes by 2.1%, this figure was 3.6% in 2018, 2.0% in 2019, and 2.2% in 2020. Based on the data in Table 3.37, we can see that in the structure of the population's incomes, incomes from agriculture and self-employment decreased during the years 2013-2020, while incomes from employment increased during this period. Thus, while income from agriculture was 41.5% of the income structure in 2013, this figure increased to 43.4% in 2020, and income from self-employment was 25.7% in 2013, but 21.8% in 2020. In the structure of consumption expenditures, we can see that expenditures on basic food products increased during 2013-2020. While expenditures on food products were 91.8 manats in 2013, accounting

for 41.55%, in 2020 they reached 129.2 manats, accounting for 43.4%. While the population's expenditures on food products increased by 37.4 manats, or 40.7%, consumption expenditures increased by 76.4 manats, or 34.5% in total during 2013-2020. Thus, the growth rate of food expenditures of the population has outpaced the growth rate of consumption expenditures. Based on the data in the table, we can say that the income of the population increased by 76.7 manats, or 35.7%, in 2013-2020, and during this period, the population's expenditures on food products increased by 37.4 manats, or 40.7%, outpacing income growth. The growth of consumption expenditures on food products accounted for 48.8% of the growth of the population's income during this period. The main reason for this is the increase in the per capita consumption of food products and the increase in the price of food products during this period.

Table 6

Share of local agricultural products, raw materials and agricultural products in the total volume of their resources
(by product type), %

№	Product name	The threshold of the food security doctrine. %	2015	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2022 limit to limit +/-
1.	Wheat	95	54,8	64,8	57,2	57,1	61.5	56.7	-38.3
2.	Potato	95	89,1	90,8	87,8	90,6	88.8	89.0	-6.0
3.	Vegetables (all types)	85	103,4	115,0	112,0	110,4	106.6	106.8	+21.8
4.	Fruits and berries	85	113,7	123,2	123,1	116,3	122.9	123.9	+38.9
5.	Milk and dairy products	90	84,3	86,7	86,3	83,5	84.8	83.3	-6.7
6.	Eggs	85	99,7	101,5	101,8	100,0	99.1	100.3	+15.3
7.	Flour (all types)	95	95,1	95,9	95,6	95,4	95.0	93.3	-1.7
8.	Sugar	80	192,9	81,7	75,0	69,4	100.7	103.9	+23.9
9.	Confectionery products with sugar	80	17,8	25,6	29,8	30,7	34.2	30.6	-49.4
10.	Beef and meat products	85	91,8	85,1	86,1	87,4	91.9	93.0	+8.0
11.	Mutton and goat meat, meat products	85	99,3	98,1	97,6	97,3	98.2	97.0	+12.0
12.	Poultry and meat products	85	98,6	75,9	74,6	79,0	79.6	78.3	-6.7
13.	Fish and fish products	80	77,6	83,1	82,2	81,7	78.2	76.7	-3.3
14.	Butter	80	69,2	71,3	69,5	62,7	66.7	62.0	-18.0
15.	Vegetable oil	80	60,5	34,3	33,6	34,8	73.2	66.7	-13.3
16.	Margarine	80	292,2	98,8	98,2	98,6	99.6	99.3	+19.3
17.	Pasta products	95	53,2	28,7	24,7	42,3	47.2	64.3	-30.7
18.	Tea	80	40,2	44,6	43,7	45,5	89.5	91.1	+11.1

Source: Statistical indicators of Azerbaijan 2023

Based on the data in the table, the dynamics that have emerged during this period give reason to say that, as before, the growth rate of prices for basic food products exceeds the growth of incomes of the population, which in turn causes the population to spend a greater part of their income on food products, and as a result, the costs that the population has to pay for other consumer needs that are important for consumption decrease, which creates difficulties in meeting other consumer needs that are important for the population. Such a situation has a negative impact on the social situation as a whole.

In recent years, the positive dynamics of agricultural production has led to an increase in the level of food independence of the country for a number of product types - grain, potatoes, vegetable oil and sugar (Table 6).

A relatively stable situation has been maintained in the consumer market for agro-food products, which was ensured by the demand of the population's solvency, and this stability was ensured mainly due to imported supplies of agricultural products, raw materials and food products, which account for almost a third of the consumption of agricultural products.

The share of local products in the structure of population consumption has not increased, and has even decreased from 67.0 percent to 66.0 percent over the past 6 years. The volume of imports of food products and agricultural raw materials amounted to 2.7 billion dollars, which was the highest compared to all previous years.

Table 7

Main socio-economic indicators of the development of the Republic of Azerbaijan

	Indicators	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
1	Population (end of year) million people	9898.1	9951	9974	10026	10063	10127
2	Gross Domestic Product (GDP) Total, million manats.	70337.8	80092.0	81896.2	72578.1	93203.2	133825.8
3	GDP per capita, manat	7205.0	8126.2	8247.0	7262.8	9269.3	13292.2
4	Average annual number of people employed in the economy, thousand people	4822.1	4879	4786	4721	4831	4901
5	Nominal income of the population, mln. manast	49162.9	53688.6	57035.0	55726.1	57181.5	68914.6
6	Average monthly nominal wages of employees, manats	525.0	544.6	635.1	707.7	732.1	840.0
7	Investments in fixed capital, mln. manats	17430.3	17244.9	18539	17226.1	16815.3	17878.2
8	Fixed assets (at the end of the year) bln. manats	182788.5	198970.4	227220.6	240694.0	259274.9	263716.4
9	Trade turnover, mln. US dollars	224103.3	30955.0	33302.7	24464.6	33911.2	52686.5
10	Export	15320.0	19489.1	19635.2	13732.6	22208.0	38146.6
11	Import	8783.3	11465.9	13667.5	10732.0	11703.2	14539.9
11	Money supply M2 at the end of the year, mln. manats	12466.4	14643.6	18238.6	20305.5	23874.9	29565.6
12	Retail turnover mln. manats	35268.1	37090.0	39391.7	40166.5	44217.5	52171.0

Source: Statistical indicators of Azerbaijan 2023

The main macroeconomic indicators of the socio-economic development of the Republic of Azerbaijan in 2017-2022 are given in Table 7. As can be seen from the data in Table 2.7, during this period,

During 2017-2022, the dynamics of growth in Gross Domestic Product (GDP) was evident. Thus, compared to 2017, GDP increased by 63488.0 million manats and amounted to 133825.8 million manats, an increase of 1.9 times.

As can be seen from the data in Table 7, the average monthly nominal wages and nominal incomes of the population increased during 2017-2022. The average monthly nominal wages of the population during this period increased by 315.0 manats from 525.0 manats in 2017 to 840.0 manats in 2022, an increase of 60.0% compared to 2017. The nominal income of the population during this period increased by 19751.7 million manats and amounted to 68914.6 million manats in 2022, an increase of 40.2% compared to 2017. We can also see this from the almost identical 47.9% increase in retail turnover in 2022 compared to 2017. In 2022, imports of goods increased by 5756.6 million US dollars, or 65.5%, compared to 2017, and exports amounted to 22826.6 million US dollars during this period. US dollars, or 2.5 times, industrial production remained at the level of the previous year on average, that is, the 62.7% increase in trade turnover was mainly provided by an increase in exports.

In 2022, the consumer price index in the country increased by 13.9%, and the money supply by 23.8%.

Loans in the banking sector are still very expensive: from 15% to 25% per annum for the real sector, and even higher for small businesses.

The development of the agro-industrial complex is carried out in accordance with the priority areas provided for in the State Program. In accordance with the State Program, special attention is paid to creating conditions for the development of rural areas, increasing employment and income from entrepreneurial activity of the population, developing cooperation in rural areas, and supporting small business initiatives. The main priority is, first of all, to maintaining the investment attractiveness of agricultural production through the fulfillment of obligations by the state on the attracted and attracted investment loans.

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